

APPLICATION OF MODELS AND METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE LEVEL OF INFORMATION PROTECTION

Kanoatov Baxtshod Oybek o'g'li

Master's degree, Faculty of Cyber-Security,
Tashkent University of Information Technologies
named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Uzbekistan

Abstract. New technologies provide much more progressive ways of working with information. Access to information is provided from anywhere, without georeferencing. All this causes the emergence of new threats and vulnerabilities. An important task is to ensure the security of data, identify compliance of protection systems with the regulatory framework and current threats to information security. Timely audit allows to confirm the necessary level of security or to notify about its shortcomings. The paper presents a developed model for assessing the security of information using intellectual means. The software algorithm for auditing the security status of an automated system for an information security specialist has been implemented and tested. The article presents implemented software for auditing the system of protection of automated systems. The preliminary data of approbation of the developed algorithm and program complex are demonstrated.

Key words: Cyber-security, hardware, software, network communication.

Introduction. In the period of active implementation and use of information technologies in various spheres of human activity, there are various threats to the security and integrity of the data used. Information technologies provide the storage of data on electronic media and distributed networks, different information processing occurs by means of automated systems. Taking into account the development of the technologies it is needed to ensure information security. During the life cycle of information from receiving, to storage and destruction it is necessary to conduct a quality audit of information security to prevent loss of information at

any these periods. Quality audit determines compliance with regulatory and legal component and defines if the organization hardware-software complex of information security is up to date. Currently, information is one of the main assets which has special value and must be properly protected. In consequence, there is the problem of increasing number of threats and vulnerabilities.

1 Confidentiality guarantees access to information to only specified people.

2 Integrity ensures that only a certain number of people can change information.

3 Availability ensures the unhindered and constant access to information for only specified group of people.

When building information security systems, control processes of the adequacy of the measures and protection means, as well as identifying vulnerabilities in the existing information system, are important. Information security audit allows to carry out such monitoring and to identify new vulnerabilities. Scientific school of Professor A. A. Shelupanov is actively involved in design of protection systems using various models of information security. The authors are conducting research aimed at implementing and improving various types of information security mechanisms. The authors consider the issue of evaluating the security of information, in particular the developed model of documents workflow, which involves action on the information in completely different mediums. Increased economic losses due to weak system of of the information protection and out-of-time the audit are considered in many papers. The authors of consider the impact of the relationship between internal audit and information security functions. The paper presents a research model that reflects the components of the audit system. At the time of the audit the authors propose to integrate the process users to identify the specific human factors and possible risks.

Material. The relevance of the topic is justified by the development of technology and the widespread introduction of information technologies for information processing, storage and transmission.

Method. Evaluation criteria for information technology security”. To develop assessment model of information security the block structure of the system is used in figure 1. The collection of information starts in the ”input data Analysis” block.

Within this step, we define the composition of the test system (software, hardware, data bases, documentation, existing or proposed (or existing) network communication). The determination of the elements of the protection system, current settings, access levels, etc. are carried out on the survey basis. The task of model development for auditing the security state of information is developing the algorithm, which allows to increase the quality and speed of audit. In addition, the algorithm should include the possibility of independent decision-making in certain cases. To solve the tasks, the following methods and techniques are used: theory of algorithms, database technology, expert evaluation method, the theory of artificial intelligence, methodology of protection of object-oriented programming. The model assumes that the system must fully meet the requirements of the legislation in the field of information security system. Estimation of security is formed using criteria GOST R ISO/IEC 15408 Information technology (IT). Methods and means of security. Evaluation criteria for information technology security”. To develop assessment model of information security the block structure of the system is used in figure 1. The collection of information starts in the ”input data Analysis” block. Within this step, we define the composition of the test system (software, hardware, data bases, documentation, existing or proposed (or existing) network communication). The determination of the elements of the protection system, current settings, access levels, etc. are carried out on the survey basis. A list of questionnaires is generated for the survey. The results of the survey form part of the input for the unit is ”Intelligent means”. The formation of the main requirements for information security system is based on the class of the used automated system, determined in accordance with the relevant documents.

Result. The object of the research is the organization system of information security. For the analysis the data of 20 organizations were used, for each the different classes of automated systems were defined. For each organization a full cycle of studies were completed. In accordance with it the following results compliance with systems for the protection of organizations were obtained. The study shows that almost all organizations have high-quality security systems, with only a

few exceptions. However, after the application of the intellectual means of calculation, possible threats have been identified. In the process of several runs, there was the neural network training to reduce the errors of the first and second kind. The analysis of the subject area studies identified the possibility of developing an assessment model of information security with intellectual means elements. This model is the basis for the algorithm and implementing software for an information security specialist, created in order to analyze and evaluate the quality of information security in the automated system. The relevance of the topic is justified by the development of technology and the widespread introduction of information technologies for information processing, storage and transmission.

Conclusion. The development of technologies and their widespread implementation requires special attention to the systems of information protection. The presented model and the implemented audit software for a information security specialist allows to solve a number of problems:

- 1 Boosting the audit conduction.
- 2 Improving the quality of the audit.
- 3 Using the list of relevant threats and vulnerabilities from the data bank FSTEC allows to maintain a system of auditing up-to-date.
- 4 The fact that elements of intellectual means allow to obtain possible solution when upgrading system protection.
- 5 The fact that saving the results of each audit at a particular organization provides tracking of changes in security system in dynamics.

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